

The Concept of Knowledge Management it's Impact on Indian Companies

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge management management is one of the most prevalent jokes in circuits. It is a means of creating a strategic impact. Theoretically cognitive management has the ability to affect many spherical structures of a company. He took into account several stages of knowledge management (knowledge production, knowledge codification and knowledge transfer and knowledge application) and understood data based on calculations for each parameter. Final conclusions were drawn based on Knowledge Management Index. Data explanation, the Knowledge Management Index (KMI) is very high according to pre-defined rating criteria for understanding and commitment, but requires involvement of top management in the allocation of resources required to initiate and retain knowledge management practice.

Keywords: *knowledge management; IT companies; Knowledge Management.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the competition about the importance of knowledge management is based on success. Knowledge is considered to be a dynamic resource, valued only when used. When companies are routinely taking time and trying to review what they know, knowledge becomes an asset to support intentional activities.

The paper currently provides the best practices in knowledge management and investigates the understanding and implementation of KM principles and practices in Indian Information Technology (IT) companies. A deliberate sample of 10 IT companies in North India was selected for study and a survey

was conducted with the objective of research management of knowledge management and implementation. The current research work is based on the second data obtained from 10 IT companies.

The Knowledge Management Index (KMI) predefined the DDD rating scale for information, awareness and commitment of information is very high, but requires the involvement of outstanding management to allocate resources for starting and maintaining knowledge management. Many people have made it clear that they are getting ready to know something about the importance of the documentation. Knowledge Management (KM) exists in our society after the discovery of language. Learned how to transfer knowledge from academics through knowledge transfer, knowledge transfer, infant, teacher, educated, literary forms, songs, dances, or folklore. While society is not widely spread, these different tools and techniques are meant to facilitate the transformation of knowledge.

Some companies have acquired Knowledge Management (KMM) in India. The Goddess Neela, Paint-Maker, adopted Knowledge Management on March 2003, as it needed to extract knowledge from consumer buyers and dealer insights.

In addition to the money paid for the product, consumers provide information on their product and the understanding of similar alternatives. Strategic challenge is in the design of an interface, which allows easy access to customer information. Know Knowledge Management Portal of Larson & Toubro (Construction Company) to solve problems that occur on project sites. It uses KM to send out the

construction of the real world construction projects at a lower cost. Every employee in the company has experienced years and does not know it to create a problem solving or strategy. The strategic challenge is to know people 'who know' and to share it with others, to express it and make it clear. Infosys Technologies (software producer) uses its KM

Knowledge management and influence of Indian companies

Knowledge Management Index for IT companies is 2.75%. It is average according to the pre-defined rating scale. People do not live directly to share knowledge. Knowledge management priority is given in the performance assessment system, and the benefits of KM are considered throughout the organization.

There is a lot of awareness that the Cultural Organization is not willing to share and practice. Efforts to develop organizational culture, acquire, share, and learn in the organization. Admins need to experience the basic steps of the management administration at different levels as needed, including knowledge management practices. This allows change agents for this initiative and dissipates all the concepts that are pre-emphasized about the success of knowledge management in these organizations.

The current magazine also suggests that a combination of traditional and innovative approaches can recognize and share the knowledge of knowledge. Knowledge Asset Authors, Critics and Customers can earn Knowledge Currency Units (KCUs), which can translate rewards to meet predetermined entry values and specified calendar milestones. Individual KCU aceles are shown on some scoreboards. Therefore, it is suggested that these institutions provide incentives for knowledge sharing. It is important to reduce the value of shared knowledge in the ongoing evaluation of performance and periodic merit reviews in the organization, thereby promoting managers and staff that the Knowledge Sharing Company is one of the major behaviors that promotes and encourages.

Knowledge management is basically fundamentally fundamentally a work of information management and information transmitting, which can be understood and utilized, and for this purpose requires effort to have knowledge repository skills, experience, assignments, exclusives and publications of publications in the future, For problem solving Inini used. The periodic knowledge management quests are

required to evaluate the knowledge gap by searching for the best practices.

Over the past two decades, local economies have been transformed into global economies. Started with India in the 1990s in India, this globalization has evolved into one of the world's most prominent athletes worldwide, capable of delivering low quality labor and infrastructure. After liberalization, the Indian economy saw significant growth and expansion in various industry sectors. Since the early 1990s, economic growth in India has contributed to the rapid growth of manufacturing and service sector. The manufacturing sector is the backbone of the Indian economy, which promotes development, productivity, employment, agriculture and service sector. Information Technology (IT) and Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) have played a major role in the development of the service sector.

Manufacturing sector in India

The Indian manufacturing sector has contributed to the Indian economy. After opening the economy, there has been a significant increase in employment and agriculture in the field of agriculture and services. The Indian manufacturing sector is divided into automotive parts / engineering, chemicals, petroleum, fertilizers, packaging, electric, electronics, IT hardware and peripherals, basic metals, textiles and other products.

The Indian economy contributes to 29 per cent of GDP in the manufacturing sector. In emerging economies in the world, India's manufacturing base is the fourth-largest and fastest growing. Over the last few years (2004-2008) this sector has an average of 9 per cent and impressive 12.5 per cent in 2006-2007. Look at India as a great force for manufacturing people around the world, the process of engineering, engineering and technology. This resulted in the development of a worldwide community of operations.

Information Technology (IT) and Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) Sector

India's service sector is more than half that is 54 per cent of GDP. The four major areas of IT in India are: IT services; IT-based services (ITES); Software; And e-business. According to NASSCOM (2006), the most visible growth is in Information Technology (IT) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services. The Indian IT industry has played an important role in the

growth of science industry in India. Countries around the world, officials, business leaders and academics have mentioned the success story of this field. The Indian private sector has contributed significantly to the growth of the sector.

Electricity in India

The Power Sector is mainly the state of the state in India and is dominated by state-owned enterprises at national and state level; 88% of government generators (power utilization of state-owned utility in the country produces state production up to 60%), and transmission is almost entirely within the public sector.

The planned development of the Indian economy began in 1950 with the independence. Since then the power sector has made significant progress. The main sources of electricity generating hydroelectric and thermal energy. Nuclear energy also reduces dependency. There is a big gap between demand and supply and the power industry is constant pressure for the same bridge.

About KMM size in three industry pairs, IT enabled services are better than the other two. Nevertheless, it is necessary to find ways to develop certain specific indicators to manage knowledge management, maintain knowledge and maintain balance between financial and non-financial indicators. Piliandian (2005) found that Indian companies did not participate in industry-based research groups to create new knowledge. Creation of new knowledge requires continuous education-industry interaction. Our findings emphasize the importance of benchmarking and audit to develop indicators to assess the KM initiative.

In order to effectively compete in reforms and knowledge economies, it is important to develop the capabilities of companies such as systems, systems, technology, culture and leadership. Leadership plays a key role in creating, developing and organizing company capabilities by creating effective teams in a diverse workforce; Tap talent across the organization by employing employment, retention and development at all levels; Combinations and acquisitions are constructing and connecting cultures to become common; Use IT to enable and integrate KM processes; Develop rewards and recognition systems for employee commitment towards organizational vision. Finally, human resource capacity to manage the characteristics of KM

separates the good and great institutions and has changed its long-term success and stability.

Conclusion

The purpose of carrying out this research work was also to identify challenges in the generation of organizational knowledge. The four major challenges were identified based on primary and secondary data in generating organizational knowledge out of individual knowledge. The first challenge was to unload the burden of experience out of organizational history. This experience interferes with the receiving and processing of new knowledge as people continue referring to precedents and past events (stories) in order to defend current practices and eliminating the need for new knowledge. It blinds people from critically analyzing and confronting new data or information. Therefore, unlearning of these experiences does not happen. The next challenge was to break organizational defensive routines. Defensive routines are written or unwritten norms of behaviors in organizations, which people perceive as given, or the most 'rational thing to do'. Defensive routines prevent people from receiving new ideas, knowledge, processes, demands, etc., that do not fit with organizational norms. Change becomes difficult, as people do not want to confront reality. The third challenge in generating organizational knowledge was to overcome people's tunnel vision. People tend to view the context from their own perspective rather than adopting a systems point of view. Another challenge that impedes the generation of organizational knowledge was bounded rationality as people look for satisfying solutions, rather than optimizing ones. Finally, it can be concluded that for organizations to remain competitive and at the forefront, workers must sort knowledge from the information overload that continues to grow at an alarming rate. In addition to linking knowledge with business strategies, it is crucial to remove cultural barriers and create a supportive climate for knowledge management to flourish. Active management support is essential to ensure that cultural elements are in place. Ideally, management fosters a collaborative climate for creating and sharing knowledge, provides recognition and rewards to those who significantly contribute to the knowledge effort, and provides technological resources to facilitate the access, use and sharing of the knowledge. HR professionals have to realize that true competitive advantage lies in the people and the best HR practices should be aligned to

strengthen knowledge management and if only this can be done by the HR professionals based on a Knowledge Management Index, this will be the best practice in managing knowledge

Reference

- 1) Knowledge management practices in Indian information technology companies by Abhilasha Singh
- 2) Knowledge Management Practices in Indian Organizations—A Sectoral Comparison by Himanshu Joshi
- 3) Collinger, A.S., & Smith, R.D. (2001). Managing organizational knowledge as a strategic asset. *Journal of Knowledge Management*,
- 4) Knowledge management practices in Indian industries – a comparative study by Deepak Chawla
- 5) Demystifying Knowledge Management in Indian Manufacturing SMEs Hari Vasudevana , Anup Chawan
- 6) <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/0972262916651534>

